

IMPACT STRENGTH AND FRACTURE TOUGHNESS
OF STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES*

George C. Chang
Associate Professor
Aerospace Engineering Department
U. S. Naval Academy
Annapolis, Maryland 21402

Basic concepts of impact testing for the evaluation of impact strength (energy) of engineering materials are discussed, along with the determination of fracture toughness by the linear elastic fracture mechanics approach. Emphasis is placed on their applications to evaluating fiber-reinforced composite materials for high-performance structures or devices. The state-of-the-art in impact testing of composites is analyzed, with significant results summarized. These include the impact strengths of a number of composites, such as graphite/epoxy, glass/epoxy, boron/aluminum, etc. Also discussed are observed failure modes. Results of a series of Izod and Charpy tests, which were carried out in the present study are discussed in some detail. The tests were designed to study such factors as: direction of impact, freezing, seawater submersion, and impact strengths of polyester and epoxy composites with glass cloth or woven roving. Most advanced composites are found to be relatively brittle, with the possible exception of S-glass/epoxy. Their impact strengths or fracture toughness values are only small fractions of those of conventional metallic materials. Some ways of improving composite toughness are also discussed.

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Introduction

In the world of engineering, structural materials of all kinds must be properly characterized before they can be efficiently utilized. The characterization of mechanical properties which is of primary interest to structural engineers, consists of stress-strain relations, thermal expansion coefficients, hardness, ductility, etc., when subjected to various types of loading. Such characterization, however, remains incomplete without mentioning the terms impact strength and fracture toughness.

Impact strength is a measure of the energy, commonly expressed in foot-pounds, required to break a material under investigation. Fracture in a structural material can be defined as an inhomogeneous process of deformation which causes regions of material to separate and load-carrying capacity to decrease to zero. Thus, fracture toughness (G) which is defined as the rate of release of elastic strain energy, provides a quantitative measurement of resistance to fracture in a material. Sometimes, the stress intensity factor (K) which is closely related to fracture toughness, is used for the same purpose.

Traditionally, the impact behavior of homogeneous, isotropic materials has been largely determined with the aid of a standard Izod test or a Charpy test.^(1,2)* Similar tests, such as drop-ball tests, miniature Charpy test, instrumented Charpy test, etc., have also been reported in special studies. With the advent of seemingly superior fiber-reinforced composite materials, it has become necessary in recent years for the engineering community to gain a basic understanding of impact behavior of such advanced materials. For various reasons, the state-of-the-art in impact strength of advanced structural composites remains relatively undernourished.^(3,4,5) Much work remains to be done.

Likewise, fracture toughness of structural materials can be determined by the compliance test within the context of linear elastic fracture mechanics.⁽⁶⁾ Relevant aspects of this approach to the evaluation of toughness of composites are discussed in this paper.

The subject of impact by foreign objects is not treated here. Discussions on it can be found in Reference 4, among others.

Impact Strength and Fracture Toughness

In this section, the basic concepts of impact testing for the evaluation of impact strength of engineering materials are dis-

*Numbers in parentheses refer to entries in references.

cussed, along with the determination of fracture toughness in linear elastic fracture mechanics approach (LEFM). Emphasis is placed on their application to evaluating composites for high-performance structures or devices.

Toughness and Ductility of Structural Materials

The toughness of an engineering material is defined as the work (or energy) per unit volume required to cause fracture. In a simple tension test, this work is expressed by:

$$\text{Work per unit volume} = \int_0^{\epsilon_f} \frac{Pdx}{AL} = \int_0^{\epsilon_f} \sigma d\epsilon$$

where A and L are cross-sectional area and length of specimen, respectively. (7) P is the applied load, dx is the increment of extension. Also, σ is the stress, while ϵ is the strain, ϵ_f is the strain at which the fracture takes place. The toughness is, therefore, simply the area under the true stress-strain curve.

Now, this term toughness is not the same as "ductility", which is a measure of the strain the material experiences under loading to cause rupture. A most common way to describe ductility is to give the percent reduction in cross-sectional area at fracture.

Incidentally, a slightly different way of measuring ductility is done by obtaining the axial elongation in a tensile test. Indeed this data is widely relied upon by engineers, as evidenced by the wealth of such data. (8)

Now, the definition of toughness given above can hardly be implemented in practice, because of stresses and strains in the vicinity of the crack tip are not so easy to measure. For engineering purposes, there exist two approaches to measuring, or representing toughness of a structural material. The first involves the impact strength concept. Two of the most widely utilized methods in this approach are the Izod and the Charpy test. (4,9) In these tests, the impact energy required to fracture a standard specimen is recorded. Low values of impact energy which is traditionally (wrongly) termed impact strength, is indicative of low values of material toughness. More on the impact strength will be discussed in subsections which follow.

A second approach to measuring toughness involves the use of fracture toughness based on the classical LEFM. This Griffith-Irwin approach itself is rather involved, particularly when it comes to dealing with advanced composite materials. (6) A brief account of this sophisticated approach is also given herein.

It must be pointed out that the above approaches were initially developed for conventional (isotropic, homogeneous) materials. However, in recent years they have been adapted to testing fiber reinforced composite materials. There exists no valid reason disapproving such adaptation. (4,10)

Evaluation of Toughness by Impact Testing

When some steels were found to be brittle around the turn of the century, Mr. Izod successfully proposed the use of an apparatus which measured the energy required to fracture a selected cantilever specimen in an impact test. That was how impact testing first got started.

Charpy-Izod Tests At present, the most widely used impact testers are the well-known pendulum weight impact machines developed by G. Charpy. In these machines, a carefully manufactured pendulum falls from a given height onto the specimen. The total energy needed to break the specimen is thus determined.

In the United States, the Charpy or Izod test is usually performed in accordance with ASTM Standard Test Methods. (1,3) Naturally, the specimen must be carefully prepared. So are the testing equipment and procedures.

Somewhat similar test appliances and standards are utilized in England (BS 131 in British Standard Handbook No. B) and in Germany (DIN 51222). (11)

Now, impact test results are usually expressed in terms of ft-lb or its equivalent. Sometimes, the impact strength is expressed in ft-lb per in² of the notched cross-section, or in ft-lb per linear inch of the notch length. Results of such tests are consistent within themselves, in that they usually rate a given group of materials in relatively the same order. None of these tests are absolute, as their numerical results cannot be utilized directly in structural design.

Other Impact Tests In addition to the tests discussed above, there exist a number of specialized impact tests, such as the Drop Weight Tear Test, Drop Weight Test, Drop Test, Timber Impact Test, etc. Some of which can undoubtedly be adapted to testing composites. (4)

Instrumented Impact Tests Discussed so far are testers which measure the total impact energy. Some recent developments have added other features to the standard testing. The instrumented Charpy/Izod test, for example, is capable of providing a measure of

toughness (G_{IC}). (12,13,14,15). In these tests, the dynamic (impact) load-time curve is recorded for the determination of the toughness, the energy to cause cracking, and the energy for propagation of the cracks. (4)

W. L. Server and D. R. Ireland reported a series of instrumented impact tests on specimens made from 6061-T6 aluminum, 4145 steel, and a graphite/aluminum composite, etc. (14) Some were standard or fatigue pre-cracked specimens, others were of other special design. These were tested on a conventional Satec 240 ft-lb impact tester and a Tinius Olsen 50 in-lb impact tester, both meeting ASTM Standards (E23 and D256, respectively). A standard DYNATUP (model 500) system was integrated into the testing system to monitor the time histories of both the impact energy and the impact force. It was found that the total impact energy values obtained from Izod and Charpy tests were quite close for both standard and pre-cracked specimens:

	<u>6061-T6 Aluminum</u>		<u>4145 Steel</u>	
<u>Tests</u>	<u>Energy</u>	<u>Force</u>	<u>Energy</u>	<u>Force</u>
Izod	11.3 ft-lb (11.1)*	800 lb (0.50)**	44 ft-lb (44.1)*	2350 lb (0.55)**
Charpy	12.3 ft-lb (12.0)*	1650 lb (0.36)**	46 ft-lb (47.0)*	4800 lb (0.5)**

*As read on conventional dial

**Time when impact reached peak in milliseconds

A second group of test results gave evidence to the existence of "approximate equivalency" between the Izod impact strength and Charpy value is given in the next section. Test performed on 24 fiberglass/epoxy specimens indicated that:

<u>Tests</u>	<u>Impact 1</u>	<u>Impact 2</u>
Izod	5.44 ft-lb	12.57 ft-lb
Charpy	5.97 ft-lb	10.88 ft-lb

It is evident, then, that it is not possible to establish absolute and complete correlation between results obtained by the Izod and the Charpy tests; an equivalency is considered existed herein. This idea is also supported by a discussion in Parts 1 to 3 of British Standards 131.

Impact Testing of Composites As outlined before, some traditional impact test methods intended for homogeneous, isotropic materials have been utilized for the testing of composites with some success. Such a practice is widely accepted. (3,9) The testing of three different composites of practical interest, as reported in next section, was conducted in this manner.

Fracture Mechanics Approach to Evaluating Toughness

The linear elastic fracture mechanics approach to the determination of fracture (initiation and propagation) behavior in engineering materials is based on the study of the stability of flaws, such as cuts, nicks, or voids. It is an outgrowth of the Griffith concept advanced in 1920. (16)

The original concept states that an existing crack will propagate in a cataclysmic fashion if the available elastic strain energy release rate exceeds the increase in surface energy of the crack. The theory gave a means for determining the correct relationship between fracture strength and size of flaws in a brittle material. Nevertheless, he did neglect the work in plastic deformation which is thought to occur at or near the crack-tip. Several authors have given useful discussions on the effect of neglecting the plasticity. (17)

The question of plasticity, however, does not seem to be so important for filamentary composites. Most composites, such as boron/epoxy and the graphite-epoxy, have rather unique stress-strain curves exhibiting abrupt ruptures at ultimate stress level. Such experimental evidence indicates that these composites possess little plasticity, or strain hardening, which is characteristic of most metals, notably the mild steel. Thus, composites seem to be more brittle than metals.

In 1955, Irwin indicated that the energy approach is equivalent to a stress-intensity approach according to which fracture occurs when a critical stress distribution, characteristic of the material, is reached. An excellent account of the review on the equivalence of these two approaches is given by Paris and Sih. (18)

Basic Relationship in LEFM A detailed derivation of fundamental relations in fracture mechanics approach to evaluating toughness can be found in Reference 6. Briefly speaking, the rate of release of elastic strain energy is

$$G = \frac{1}{2} F^2 \frac{\partial(1/k)}{\partial a} \quad (1)$$

where F is the applied load in a "compliance test," k is the ratio between F and elongation, and a is one half of the crack normal to the direction of F . As fracture toughness is defined as the work rate with respect to crack length to extend a crack, it is clear that fracture toughness is merely the critical value (upon fracture) of G . As far as physical fracture, three modes are possible: I, the direct opening mode; II, the edge-sliding mode; III, the tearing mode. Consequently, fracture toughness can be given by G_{IC} , etc., in units of in-lb/in², or its equivalent. Alternately, fracture toughness can be represented by the stress intensity factor, K , in units of ksi $\sqrt{\text{in}}$. It is noted that, for plane stress,

$$EG_{Ic} = K_{Ic}^2 \quad (2)$$

where E is the modulus of elasticity. The related fracture stress is

$$\sigma_f = \left[\frac{E}{a \cdot I_{Ic}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} = K_{Ic} \div \sqrt{a} \quad (3)$$

The corresponding equations for plane strain condition are:

$$EG_{Ic} = (1-\nu^2)K_{Ic}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$K_{Ic} = \sigma_f \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (5)$$

Now the G-value can be determined in a laboratory test by loading a suitable specimen, as described earlier. Likewise, the K-value can be determined in a test.

Fracture Toughness and Tensile Strength From equation (3), it is seen that the useful strength of a material, based on σ_f , is inversely related to the flaw size, and directly proportional to the fracture toughness which is a material property. For a given material, therefore, the useful fracture-safe stress is dependent on the flaw size, a. The smaller the flaw size, the higher the fracture-safe stress, and vice versa. This observation is clearly illustrated in Figure 1.

Fracture toughness as a material property varies from one material to another. It also varies from one grade of a material to another grade of the same material. This fact is illustrated in Figure 2. (6) Such variations are due to variance in chemical compositions, atomic arrangements, as well as processing, resulting in an-isotropy as well as flaws.

LEFM and Composites Fiber reinforced composites possess characteristics which set them apart from conventional materials. Questions have been raised whether LEFM techniques are applicable to composites. Based on investigations by a number of authors in recent years, it has been tentatively concluded that the answer is a yes. (5,6,10) Evidence gathered from several experimental programs indicates that the LEFM approach could be extended to the orthotropic materials of which the fiber composite material is one. Details of some of these observations can be found in Reference 6.

In Table II some numbers indicating fracture toughness of selected materials are given. They must be viewed within the context of the above discussions.

Impact Testing of Three Advanced Composites

In this section and the next, the state-of-the-art in impact strengths of some selected fibrous composites as determined by laboratory tests is discussed.

Impact strength of three selected fiber glass-based advanced composites was investigated by the author in a recent study. (4) A total of 108 Charpy/Izod specimens were tested. It must be pointed out that these tests were exploratory in nature. The ASTM test method for plastics (D-256) was followed, except that specimen sizes had to be slightly varied due to availability of composite plates. Nevertheless, it is felt that these thick plates used herein more closely represented real-life applications in marine industry.

Identification of Specimen Materials

All three composites were provided in the form of thick plates by the Laboratory for Advanced Composites at Naval Ship Research and Development Center. Relevant information on these materials are available at the lab. They are briefly described for the purpose of this work.

Material "A" This material was made of 181 Style Glass Cloth (8.9 ounce per square yard) in Epon 828 epoxy with 8 phrDTA (Dicythylene Triaminc) as catalyst. This 24-cloth-layered plate was made by hand layup and was cured with the use of vacuum bag at room temperature for a long time (months) prior to testing. It has an average thickness of 0.395 in.

Material "B" The material was made of 181 Style Glass Cloth (8.9 oz/sq yd) in fire-retardant Polyester (with Hetron 24370) conforming to Mil Spec C7575, with 0.2 phr Co Naphthenate (a promoter) and catalyst: 1 phr Methyl Ethyl/Ketone Peroxide. The plate contained 19 layered cloth in an average thickness of 0.320 inch. It was made by hand layup and cured in vacuum bag at room temperature for a long period of time before testing.

Material "C" This composite plate was made of G-135 Glass Fiber Woven Roving (24 oz/sq yd) in the fire retardant polyester used for material "B". Similar promoter and catalyst were also used. The plate was made by hand layup and air-cured at room temperature for a long time before testing. It has an average thickness of 15/32 or 0.469 in., containing 16 layups.

Impact Specimens

It is noted that standard impact test specimens have a cross-

section of 0.394 in. x 0.394 in. At the notch, the net section is 0.394 in. x 0.315 in., with a notch length of 0.394 in.

Three groups of specimens were used:

Group "A" Specimens which were cut from plate material "A" described above were the most numerous. Each Charpy specimen had a standard 2.165 in. length. Some were un-notched. Others has a 45° V-notch ($r=0.010$ in. standard). In all cases, the net notched sections measured 0.315 in. x 0.395 in. Notch length was 0.395 in. It was found that most notches had a depth of 0.080 in. as compared to the standard depth of 0.079 inch.

Some specimens had notches cutting through the thickness, with notches running perpendicular to cloth layups. This type of specimen was called Type I, as shown in Figure 3. The specimen, of course, would be struck in a manner similar to conventional Charpy test. The other specimen, Type II, had a notch cutting through only a few cloth layers. The notch was actually parallel to the cloth layer.

Now, twelve Izod specimens were also fabricated out of material "A". Half of them were of Type I, the rest being Type II. They were similar to the Charpy except the specimen length and location of the notch. All were made to conform to standard practice.

Group "B" These Charpy specimens were used to compare epoxy with polyester as matrix materials. Owing to the fact that plate "B" had only a thickness of 0.320 in., it was decided to make Charpy specimens with two different sizes:

Type I - Cross section 0.315 in. x 0.320 in. Notch length 0.320 in.

Type II - Cross section 0.241 in. x 0.395 in. Notch length 0.395 in.

Standard 45° V-notches were used.

Group "C" This Charpy group represented the simplest. No notches were made. The dimensions were as follows:

Type I - Cross section 0.395 in. x 0.469 in. Imaginary notch length 0.469 in.

Type II - Cross section 0.469 in. x 0.395 in. Imaginary notch length 0.395 in.

Incidentally, all specimens were cut from the composite plates with high-speed sharp cutters. Each specimen had a standard length

of 2.165 in.

Lastly, the specimens are to be designated by two letters and three numbers, e.g., AI-101. Here "A" refers to material type "A"; "I" is for type "I" which indicates the notch direction as well as the corresponding physical impact; the first number signifies that the specimen would be utilized in the first test, the last two numbers represent specimen number in a given test.

Those specimens which are not notched are indicated by (NN), e.g., AI-201(NN), etc.

Specimens subject to freezing effect were prepared in the same way as those for Test No.1. They were placed in freezing compartment of a lab refrigerator for twenty-four hours prior to testing. The measured temperature in that compartment was -2°C or 28.4°F .

For Tests 3 and 4, specimens were placed in "sea-water" obtained off the U. S. Naval Academy. All specimens experienced a submergence period of seven days prior to immediate testing.

Impact Failure Modes

Conventional impact strength tests were conducted, using 108 composites specimens described earlier. Total Charpy or Izod energy levels were recorded.

All tests were conducted at room temperature. In the case of Test No. 5, the specimens which were frozen in the freezing compartment of a lab refrigerator were tested within a minute, or less, upon removal from the freezer.

Representative failure modes observed in these tests are shown in Figure 4.

Specimens generally failed in either of two modes: cleavage (direct cracking) and delamination. Freezing or water submersion did not seem to result in different failure modes.

Specimens identified as D and C, i.e., No. AI-104 and AII-106, respectively, were closely photographed as shown in Figures 5 and 6. The direct cracking nature of failure mode for specimen AI-104 is clearly shown. Some fiber pull-outs (of small length) seem to have taken place. Also clearly visible is the "plastic/cracked" zone running from the notch to the opposite side of specimen. Obviously, this was a heavily stressed zone during the impact. It's typical of the Type I specimens tested.

Now, specimen AII-106 failed in a manner which suggested a combination of delamination and cleavage cracking. The former seemed dominant. The latter could be caused by bending during the

"energy propagation" phase of the failure.

Testing of the no-notch specimens resulted in similar failure modes in notched specimens. They are shown in Ref. 4.

The no-notch specimen CI-902(NN) failed in a slightly different manner. Perhaps the woven roving was too strong for the cleavage action to take place clearly. Some form of in-place twist took place, accompanied by fiber pull-outs as well as debonding. Small wonder that it resulted in a very high impact strength.

Now, the woven-roving specimen CII-901(NN) failed in a distinctive delamination mode. Nearly all layers separated from each other.

From above discussions, it becomes clear that impact failure modes of composites studied are definitely direction dependent. Type I notched specimens (see: notch direction and the blow) failed in modes clearly cleavage in nature, while Type II specimens failed in delamination, accompanied by small amounts of cleavage failures. It is further noted that failure of Type II specimens showed some residual strength, as in most cases the specimens remained one-piece. This is in contrast to failures of some steel impact specimens, which show only cleavage cracking, resembling Type I failure modes discussed herein.

Testing of Izod specimens resulted in similar failure modes as those of the Charpy specimens.

Analysis of the Tests

Summarized in Table I are the average results of the testing program. Several significant parameters designed into the testing series are discussed below.

Basic Impact Strength From Test No. 1, it can be seen this particular composite material possesses a relatively low impact strength when compared to some tough conventional materials such as mild steels and aluminum alloys. For example, the Charpy value for a standard specimen made from the tough AISI C1018 grade steel is approximately 36 ft-lb, with a corresponding I.S./L of 90 ft-lb/in, and its I.S./A is 289 ft-lb/sq in. (19) The rather brittle steel, C1090, is believed to have an I.S. of 5 ft-lb. Hence, composite material "A" is considered to possess low impact strength. This fact is also reflected in Tests No. 2 through 6.

The rather low impact strength is inherent in the constituent materials, particularly the epoxy matrix. Ordinary epoxy has a low impact strength of 0.2 to 1.7 ft-lb/in. (20) Phenolic resins are much worse, while Polyester resins may be comparable to epoxy (0.4 to 1.5 ft-lb/in.).

Incidentally, the Izod (which is comparable to Charpy) value given on page 82 of Ref. 20, for a composite material (conventional epoxy/MPDA 181-Style Glass Cloth, 33% resin) was 12 to 15 ft-lb. No mention was made of the directions of notch and impact. This number is close to the AII-1 results.

Directional Dependence of Impact Strength That impact strength is highly direction dependent is clearly shown by results of Test No. 1. The AI specimens have an impact strength of only about 60% that of the AII specimens. This fact is also shown in Tests No. 2 through 8.

It was observed that AI specimens having a notch cutting through the thickness (therefore all cloth layers), failed in the simple cleavage modes, as discussed in last subsection. Even those AI(NN) specimens which were also struck in the "I" direction, failed in cleavage modes. Relatively little work was expanded in achieving such a fracture, which explained the low impact values observed.

On the other hand, the AII specimen (as well as AII(NN)'s) failed in a completely different mode: Delamination and, to a much less extent, cleavage fracture. This required larger amounts of energy.

Test No. 9 involved specimens with woven-roving/polyester. The direction-dependence factor is even more pronounced, although the CI-value was higher than that of CII. The former failed in delamination modes only, whereas the latter failed in delamination as well as cleavage cracking.

Notching The introduction of notches to a test specimen reduces the impact strength. This is evident by comparing results between Tests No. 1 and 2. The no-notch "Charpy" specimens of AI-2 scored about 50% more impact energy values than the standard ones. A similar situation existed in Tests No. 3 and 4, as well as in Tests 7 and 8.

Seawater Submersion Those seven-day-seawater-soaked specimens of glass cloth/epoxy were tested to detect any deterioration which might be present following seawater submersion. When results of Test No. 3 are compared with that of Test No. 1, the only sensible conclusion is a simple no-effect. Same is true between Tests 4 and 2. Some may even argue, based on the impact strengths observed from those 48 specimens, that impact strengths went up slightly. However, this is considered not certain, as the change was on the order of several percent, which is comparable to the accuracy of the Tinius-Olsen tester.

Nevertheless, epoxy is known to have absorbed water at a slow rate (about 0.05-0.07% by weight over 24 hour period, see page 82

of Reference 20). The absorbed water may have an effect on impact strength of the composites. However, this was not clearly detected in these tests.

Izod versus Charpy Values From results of Tests No. 1 and 6, it can be said that values of Charpy impact strength are approximately the same as those of the Izod, when similar (notch, sections, directions) specimens are utilized. The theoretical discussion on this was given in Section 2.6.1 of Reference 4.

Epoxy versus Polyester Judging from test results (No. 1 and 7), the impact strength of the epoxy based material "A" seems to be somewhat inferior to that of the polyester-based material "B". This is evidenced by considering the impact strength per unit notch length, and the impact strength/square inch of the net notched-section. This tentative conclusion, of course, is of rather limited implications, as the two matrices are known to have various grades.

Woven Roving versus Cloth The impact performance of material "C" seemed impressive with impact strength rated at 67.91 ft-lb/in and a 171.88 ft-lb/sq in., for the Type I loading (no-notch). Thus, it is nearly two-thirds as good as the AISI C1018 tough steel. This woven roving/polyester material seemed much more superior to the 181 cloth/polyester (see Test No. 7 for numbers) or the 181 cloth/epoxy (see Tests No. 1 or 2).

It must be pointed out, though, that the woven roving is a much heavier material than the cloth. In addition, specimens in Test No. 9 were not notched. Further, these specimens were having larger dimensions than the rest. Size of specimens may have an effect on the impact strength ratings. It is worthy of further investigations.

Additional Impact Testing of Composites

Results of a number of impact testing programs have been reviewed. Several of them are discussed herein.

Novak's Resin Composites

Results of a series of Charpy impact testing on resin matrix composites tested in the strongest fiber direction were reported in Ref. 21. Many strong fibers were used, including the S-Glass from Owens-Corning, and boron fibers from Hamilton Standard. For the most part, the matrix materials were Union Carbide epoxies, ERL2256/27pph0820 or ERLA-4617/23pph m -PDA or BP-907 from American Cyanamid.

Impact testing was conducted on Charpy V-notch (ASTM E23-64, Type A) specimens at room temperature. Fiber volume ratio for all composites were 55%. Impact energy observed varied widely:

<u>Composite</u>	<u>Impact Strength (ft-lb)</u>
HMG-50/ERL-2256 epoxy	4.5
Courtraulds C/ERL-2256 epoxy	10
Courtraulds HM/ERL-2256 epoxy	8
Courtraulds HM/Lexan polycarbonate*	9
Morganite IS/ERL-2256 epoxy**	3
HMG-50/ERL-2256 epoxy**	3
Boron/ERL-2256 epoxy	8 to 14
Boron/Skybod 700 polyimide	10
S-Glass/ERL-2256 epoxy	54

**Treated fiber

*tough resin

It can be seen that composites with S-glass have the highest impact strength, nearly comparable to some moderately tough steels. Boron/epoxy composites prove to be a material with low impact resistance. Graphite/epoxy composites scored the lowest.

The use of "tough" epoxy (polycarbonate) as the matrix for graphite composites produces no significant increase in impact strength. Further, composites with surface-treated graphite fibers have lower impact strength.

In this study, it was found that the toughness of composites was largely determined by the stress-strain behavior of the fibers. The toughness of the resin matrix was shown to represent a small contribution to composite impact strength.

Simon's Investigations

A series of Izod impact tests were conducted on graphite/epoxy specimens in accordance with ASTM Method D256. A second series of impact tests were also performed, using specially devised "Ring" specimens and related test fixture. (22)

The graphite/epoxy tensile specimens generally failed at a small strain of 0.5 to 1.5%. It is not surprising to find that graphite/epoxy composites possessed rather low impact strength. Simon reported Izod values ranging from 6 to 20 Joule/cm² (4.38 to 15.6 ft-lb, or 8.7 to 37 ft-lb per inch of notch length) for assorted typical graphite/epoxy composites.

Other Impact Testing Work

In Ref. 23, results of a series of impact tests utilizing a special drop-weight type apparatus were reported. It was found that impact resistance of glass-epoxy increased some 25% with increased rate of loading from 12 to 22 ft/sec. However, the HMS graphite-epoxy was found to be insensitive to rate of loading.

Results of impact testing of a series of miniature un-notched Charpy specimens (tungsten wires in copper) were reported in Ref. 24. It was found that as the diameter of tungsten wires decreased, the impact energy also decreased appreciably.

Testing of a series of un-notched miniature Izod specimens of tungsten wires in copper, nickel, and a nickel-based superalloy was reported in Ref. 25. Increased temperature was found to have raised impact energy of composites. Further, it was concluded that impact strength increased with increasing fiber content in the tungsten superalloy. That material seemed to possess an impact strength adequate for turbine blade and vane usage.

Some ten more reports of work on impact strengths of composites were reviewed in section 3.3 of Ref. 4. Some of these reports indicate that impact strength is also somewhat influenced by other factors such as: chemical composition, length of fiber, processing (thus flaw size and anisotropy), thickness, residual stress, chemical attacks, nature of loading (thus fatigue, creep, etc.), and so on. These same factors naturally influence the so-called fracture toughness of composites as well.

Practical Considerations in Composite Toughness

Toughness of composites is, as pointed out in last three sections, heavily dependent on many factors. Of interest to structural engineers are such practical indications as impact strength and fracture toughness.

Toughness of Selected Materials

Impact strengths and fracture toughness of a number of selected materials are listed in Table II for comparison purposes. Naturally, this comparison is not complete nor exact as many of the data points were obtained using a great variety of specimens as well as methods. However, the listing does cast some light on the relatively weak toughness of composites.

It should be pointed out that all test data were obtained at room temperature. Further, impact strengths for composites refer to the strongest direction. All composites listed herein are uni-

directionally reinforced.

By closely examining the impact strength (or K_{Ic} , G_{Ic}), it becomes very clear that fiber reinforced composite materials possess relatively low toughness capabilities. This is particularly true of E-glass/epoxy, graphite/epoxy, and similar materials with polyester matrix materials. However, S-glass/epoxy may be considered an exception to the low toughness classification. It may be more properly classified as one which is comparable to that of mild structural steel, or 4340 steel. It may even be considered better than titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V, or the aluminum alloy, 7075-T6. However, this observation is tentative in nature, as the evidence of its high toughness values has not been broad nor substantive.

Some composites with metal matrices seem to possess moderately high toughness. This is indeed expected, as the toughness of a composite is determined by its component materials. Here, of course, the advantage of high strength-to-weight ratio has become lost.

Finally, the so-called Type II mode failed without leading to complete instantaneous catastrophic failures. Some residual strength remained with the shattered composites.

Improvement of Toughness

Naturally, toughness of a composite can be improved through the use of improved matrix materials. Some poly-carbonates seem to possess desired qualities (26). Metal matrices, such as borsic or nickel-based alloys seem to be worthy candidates.

Proper selection of fibers is a must. For improved toughness, the S-glass seems to possess desirable qualities (see pages 3-48 of Ref. 4). The PRD-49 (now Kevlar) fibers seem very attractive, too.

Most investigations for improving toughness centered on the use of hybrid concept, namely, introducing some tough fibers into composites with brittle fibers.

A series of glass boron/epoxy and glass/graphite/epoxy composites were tested in impact (21). Hybrid composites having equal amounts of glass and high modulus fiber were found to have impact strengths three to five times as high as those of composites which were reinforced with the high modulus fiber alone. Similar results with other composites were reported in References 12, 22, and 27). In these experiments, tougher fibers such as PRD-49, steel, and S-glass were utilized.

A rather significant approach to further improvements to composite impact strength has been found recently. Drop ball impact testing at the Naval Ship Research and Development Center showed that a ten fold improvement in impact strength of S-glass/epoxy composites was attained by adhering a 0.010 in. film of polyethylene to the composite surface (28).

Conclusions

It appears that fiber-reinforced composites, such as boron-epoxy, etc., will be utilized for high-performance flight structures on an ever increasing scale in future years. However, the toughness of such composites, either in terms of impact strength or fracture toughness (G_{Ic} , etc.), has not been sufficiently characterized (4). Consequently, additional research and development in this area is very much needed.

Some impact characteristics deserve first-priority treatment in future investigations. The first one is the temperature dependence of the impact strength, including the possible existence of transition temperature. Additional factors to be studied are related to the environment: long-term weathering, water absorption as well as freezing effects for prolonged periods. Rate of loading would be more fully investigated next.

The investigation of composite toughness by Izod or Charpy impact testing in lieu of linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) testing, is generally preferred on cost as well as time-saving grounds. As discussed before, the instrumented Charpy tests can be related to results of LEFM such that fracture stress levels of some materials can be ascertained for designers. An extension of this approach to the treatment of composites may prove fruitful indeed.

Although most advanced composites possess relatively low toughness values, there is room for optimism. Better matrices, such as metal or polycarbonate, may offer desired improvements. Improvements may be achieved by coating the surface with elastomeric materials or through the use of thin metallic overlays.

Finally, improvements in impact strength may also be achieved through selective dispersment of tough fibrous materials, such as S-glass and Kevlar (PRD-49), in the composite layup.

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Table I Impact Test Results of Three Composites

I.S. = Impact strength in foot-pounds

I.S./L = I.S. per inch of notch, in ft-lb/in

I.S./A = I.S. per sq in of notched section, in ft-lb/sq in

<u>Test No.</u>	<u>Specimens</u>	<u>I.S.</u>	<u>I.S./L</u>	<u>I.S./A</u>
1. (Basic)	AI-1	5.97	15.11	47.99
	AII-1	10.88	27.54	87.46
2. (Basic, NN)	AI-2	9.83	24.89	63.01
	AII-2	16.05	40.63	102.88
3. (Water)	AI-3	6.00	15.19	48.23
	AII-3	9.93	25.14	79.82
4. (Water, NN)	AI-4	10.73	27.16	68.78
	AII-4	18.05	45.70	115.71
5. (Freezing)	AI-5	6.48	16.41	52.09
	AII-5	11.32	28.66	91.00
6. (Izod)	AI-6	5.44	13.77	43.73
	AII-6	12.57	31.83	101.05
7. (Cloth/Polyester)	BI-7	7.55	23.59	74.90
	BII-7	11.16	28.25	117.23
8. (Cloth/Polyester, NN)	BI-8	13.42	41.94	106.17
	BII-8	15.03	38.05	118.91
9. (Woven Roving/Polyester)	CI-9	31.85	67.91	171.88
	CII-9	14.25	36.08	76.90

Table II Toughness of Selected Materials**

Materials	I.S./in	I.S./in ²	G _{Ic}	K _{Ic}
	ft-lb/in	ft-lb/in ²	ft-lb/in ²	ksi√in
Gray Cast Iron	2.5(I)	8.1(I,C)		
AISI 1018 Steel	90(C)			
AISI 1090 Steel	12.5(C)			
Mild Struc. Steel, σ _u = 160 ksi (ultimate)	114(I)	360(I)		150
AISI 4340 Steel			125	64
Titanium, Ti-6Al-4V	25-51(c)	81-161(C)		125-175
Aluminum, 7075-T6			115	23-33
Aluminum, 2024-T3			300	47
Bronz	28-41(C)			
Dow 332 Epoxy			6	1.6
Epoxy, Class 105	1.3-4.3(I)	4.1-14(I)		
Polyester, Class 105	0.5-1.0(I)	1.6-3.2(I)		
Phenolic, Class 105	0.6-1.0(I)	2.0-3.2(I)		
Polycarbonate	12-18(I)			
Teflon	3.0(I)			
Glass/Epoxy, Scotchply				3.6
CSM/Polyester				3.1
Tungsten/Copper			5	
Boron/Aluminum 6061			31-42	
Scotchply, Type 1002, unidirectional		114(C)		
HMS Graphite/Epoxy Unidirectional		3.8(C)		
E-Glass Fabric/Epoxy	11-30(I)			
Graphite/Epoxy				
Modulite 5206, 52%	43-69(C)*			
Graphite/Glass/Epoxy M5206(30%), S2(27%)	16-161(C)*			
Graphite (M5206, 26%)/ PRD-49(36%)/Epoxy	7-126(C)*			
Graphite/Epoxy	8.7-37(I)			
Graphite/Epoxy, T505 & T50 & HMS	2-5.5(I)*			
PRD-49/Epoxy	6.6(I)			
S-Glass/Epoxy (49%)	17.9(I)			
Graphite/Epoxy	7.6-25(C)	24-82(C)		
Boron/Epoxy	20-36(C)	64-113(C)		
S-Glass/Epoxy (55%)	137(C)	437(C) ASTM	E23 Specimens used	

(I) Izod

(C) Charpy

*The first figure refers to energy at initiation of fracture, the second represents the total.

**See Reference 4.

1. Tensile Strength and Flaw Size

2. Stress Intensity Factor and Tensile Strength

3. Composite Charpy Specimens

4. Impact Failure Modes of Glass/Epoxy Specimens

5. Close-up of Specimen AI-104
(Enlarged approximately 8 times)

6. Close-up of Specimen AII-106
(Enlarged approximately 8 times)